

SYNTHESIS IN THE ALLOXAZINE, ISOALLOXAZINE (FLAVIN) AND LUMAZINE GROUPS. PART III. SYNTHESIS OF SOME ACID DERIVATIVES.

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The synthesis of some acids of the alloxazine and flavine groups has been undertaken for some chemotherapeutic purposes. *o*-Phenylenediamine-4-sulphonic acid and 1:2-diaminonaphthalene-4-sulphonic acid yield with alloxan the corresponding alloxazine derivatives. Flavin-9-propionic acid has been synthesised starting from *o*-nitroaniline by the method of Kuhn, but attempts to synthesise the corresponding 6-methyl derivative did not meet with success, a product, m.p. 225°, being obtained instead. 3:4-Diaminocinnamic acid yields with alloxan the corresponding alloxazine-acrylic acid.

As has been pointed out in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 627) one of the main objects of the synthesis in this series is to prepare compounds that may be least toxic to the host and also possess some specific physical and pharmacological properties. The presence of the acid groupings in the case of numerous drugs is indeed striking and this is mainly due to the fact that these groupings, besides lowering the toxicity of the compounds, form soluble sodium salts which make their administration easier and absorption more effective. The synthesis of different types of acids of the above groups has, therefore, been attempted. Kuhn and Boulanger (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1936, 241, 233) studied the lethal doses of many carboxylic acids of alloxazine and flavine groups on mice and rabbits and have found that the acid groupings decrease the toxicity of the compounds in many cases.

Kuhn and Cook (*Ber.*, 1937, 70, 764) condensed 3:4-diaminobenzoic acid with alloxan and obtained the two theoretically possible isomeric acids, alloxazine-6- and 7-carboxylic acids. It appeared to us worth while to compare these with the corresponding sulphonic acid, since in many of the dyestuffs used in chemotherapy, the presence of the sulphonic acid grouping is known to decrease the toxicity of the compound and also to possess some specific property of facilitating the absorption of the drug (Stieglitz, "Chemistry and Recent Progress in Medicine", 1926, p. 12; Ehrlich, "Studies in Immunity", 1910, p. 414). It is of interest to note that of the two drugs, solganol (I) and krysolgan (II), used in the treatment of tuberculosis, the former is less toxic, better tolerated and generally gives better results (*cf. Pai, Indian Med. Gazette*, 1928, May supplement,

p. 18; Freund, *Beitr. Klin. Tuberk.*, 1928, **68**, 606; Schröder, *Z. Tuberk.*, 1934, **70**, 408).

o-Phenylenediamine hydrochloride was sulphonated and the resulting 1:2-diaminobenzene-4-sulphonic acid (Post, *Annalen*, 1880, **208**, 100) condensed with alloxan to yield (apparently) a mixture of acids from which an acid was isolated which can be represented as either alloxazine-6-sulphonic acid (III, R=H; R'=SO₃H) or alloxazine-7-sulphonic acid (III, R=SO₃H; R'=H). This acid is comparatively more soluble in water than other alloxazine derivatives. To prepare an acid of higher molecular weight, 1:2-diaminonaphthalene-4-sulphonic acid was condensed with alloxan and the product obtained is probably 7:8-benzoalloxazine-6-sulphonic acid (IV) or 5:6-benzoalloxazine-7-sulphonic acid (V) or a mixture of both.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

Though β -naphthoquinone has been found to condense with 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate to yield benzolumazine (Kuhn and Cook, *loc. cit.*), β -naphthoquinone-4-sulphonic acid did not, however, react with the uracil to yield either (IV) or (V). This is probably due to the fact that the sulphonic acid group in β -naphthoquinone-4-sulphonic acid has a great tendency to react first with the amino group and then pass on to the α -quinonoid form (*cf.* Boniger, *Ber.*, 1894, **27**, 25).

It has been observed by Kuhn and Boulanger (*loc. cit.*) that flavin-9-acetic acid (isalloxazine-9-acetic acid, VI, R=H, $n=1$) is less toxic than the corresponding compound without the acid grouping. With an object to

find out the effect of lengthening the side-chain by one more carbon atom, in position 9, the synthesis of flavin-9-propionic acid (*isalloxazine-9-propionic acid*, VI, R=H; $n=2$) was undertaken. This compound has been synthesised very recently by Karrer, Kbner and Zehender (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1936, 19, 261) starting from *o*-nitrobromobenzene. It has now been synthesised according to the method of Kuhn and Rudy (*Ber.*, 1935, 68, 300) in better yield. *o*-Nitroaniline condensed with β -bromopropionic acid yielding *N*-(*o*-nitrophenyl)- β -aminopropionic acid (VII, R=H), which, after reduction with alkaline stannite and subsequent condensation with alloxan in acid solution, yielded flavin-9-propionic acid (VI, R=H; $n=2$).

(VI)

(VII)

In order to synthesise 6-methylflavin-9-propionic acid (VI, R=Me; $n=2$), 4-methyl-2-nitroaniline was condensed with β -bromopropionic acid to yield *N*-(4-methyl-2-nitro)- β -aminopropionic acid (VII, R=Me), which after reduction with alkaline stannite and treatment with alloxan, however, did not yield the corresponding flavin derivative but only a product, m.p. 225°, which has not yet been identified and does not appear to be either the amino compound corresponding to VII (R=Me) or the lactam derived from it. It is indeed striking that the presence of the methyl group so radically alters the course of the reaction.

It appeared to be of interest to synthesise an acid with a side-chain attached to the benzene ring and 3:4-diaminocinnamic acid was condensed with alloxan. The product obtained can be either alloxazine-6-(β)-acrylic acid (III, R=H; R'=HO₂C-CH:CH-) or alloxazine-7-(β)-acrylic acid (III, R=HO₂C-CH=CH-; R'=H) or a mixture of both. The unsaturated side chain is expected to impart to the compound some specific pharmacological properties, because cinnamic acid has been reported to give good results in the treatment of some forms of tuberculosis (Stenberg, *Z. Tuberk.*, 1927, 48, 309; cf. also Jacobsen, *Res. prakt. Biol.*, 1929, 21, 188).

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Alloxazine 6- or 7-sulphonic Acid (III).—*o*-Phenylenediamine hydrochloride (2.5 g.) was carefully added to fuming sulphuric acid (30% SO_3 , 18 c.c.) and the mixture heated on the water-bath for 4-5 hours. It was then poured into ice (about 300 g.), the dilute solution carefully neutralised with barium carbonate, filtered and the filtrate (charcoal) was concentrated on the water-bath to a small volume. The solid matter was filtered off after chilling, the filtrate made just acid with dilute sulphuric acid, the precipitated barium sulphate filtered off and the clear solution containing the sulphonic acid just warmed on the water-bath with a solution of alloxan (3 g. in 30 c.c. of water) for a few minutes, whereby the condensation product began to separate in fine yellow needles. It was filtered after allowing to stay for about an hour and then crystallised twice from boiling water. It separates in fine yellow needles which appear homogeneous. (Found: N, 18.88. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{O}_5\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires N, 19.05 per cent). The substance, probably because of its nonfusible nature,* does not decompose completely when heated with concentrated nitric acid in the bomb so that the estimation of sulphur could not be carried out accurately. It is almost insoluble in all organic solvents and comparatively more soluble in boiling water. Its solution shows a green fluorescence.

The condensation product appears to yield a mixture of two products (as judged from the crystalline form) and the isomer, other than the one described, could not be readily isolated.

7:8-Benzoalloxazine-6-sulphonic Acid (IV), *5:6-Benzoalloxazine-7-sulphonic Acid* (V).—Congo red (2.3 g.) was dissolved in boiling water (50 c.c.) and the solution mixed with ammonia (25 c.c.). On the addition of excess of zinc dust and vigorous stirring, the colour of the solution was discharged and benzidine began to separate. After about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour the solution was kept well cooled in ice for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the excess of zinc dust and benzidine carefully filtered off, the filtrate acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and warmed on the water-bath for a few minutes after the addition of a solution of alloxan (1.5 g.), when the yellow condensation product began to separate. After allowing to stand for about an hour, it was filtered and washed well with cold water and alcohol, yield 1.5 g. It separated from boiling water in orange-yellow amorphous form. (Found: N, 16.52. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires N, 16.28 per cent). It is very sparingly soluble in organic solvents

* The melting points of the compounds, wherever they are not definite, are not recorded.

and comparatively fairly soluble in boiling water from which it separates sometimes in a colloidal form very difficult to filter. It gives a cherry red colouration with concentrated sulphuric acid.

N-(*o*-Nitrophenyl)- β -aminopropionic acid (VII, R=H) has been prepared by Karrer, Köbner and Zehender (*loc. cit.*) by condensing *o*-nitrobromobenzene with β -aminopropionic ester and hydrolysing the product. It can be prepared more conveniently by the following method. An intimate mixture of *o*-nitroaniline (13.8 g.) and β -bromopropionic acid (15.3 g.) was kept at 140-50° for 1 hour (the yield is better at this temperature than at 110-20°). After cooling, the mass was triturated with dilute ammonia, filtered and the alkaline filtrate acidified under cooling with concentrated hydrochloric acid, whereby the condensation product separated. The mixture was chilled and then filtered, yield 6.5-7.5 g. It crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 141-42°. (Found: N, 13.23. $C_9H_{10}O_4N_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent).

The yield of the product in this case is far less than in the case of condensation product of *o*-nitroaniline with bromoacetic acid; it was thought that this was due to the β -position of the bromine atom. But it has been found (unpublished observation) that β -bromopropionic acid condenses with *m*-nitroaniline under the same conditions to give a good yield of *N*-(*m*-nitrophenyl)- β -amino propionic acid.

Flavin-9-(β -propionic Acid or isoAlloxazine-9-propionic Acid (VI, R=H; $n=2$).—A solution of *N*-(*o*-nitrophenyl)- β -aminopropionic acid (2.2 g.) in sodium hydroxide solution (10 %, 20 c.c.) was added with stirring to a solution of alkaline stannite, prepared from a solution of stannous chloride (9 g. in 20 c.c. of water) and sodium hydroxide (10 %, 90 c.c.). In about 10-15 minutes the red colour was discharged and the solution became light yellow indicating that the reduction was complete; the solution was added drop by drop with good stirring to alloxan (3 g.) in glacial acetic acid (75 c.c.) whereby a yellow compound separated. After about 15 minutes, the mixture was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid (15 c.c.) and after adding powdered sugar charcoal (40 g.) it was kept stirred for 1 hour when all the dyestuff was absorbed. The charcoal was filtered, washed thoroughly with warm and then cold water and the dyestuff eluted by means of pyridine-methanol-water mixture. On distilling off most of the solvent from the yellow solution showing a green fluorescence in partial *vacuo* on the water-bath, the dyestuff separated. After allowing to stand for some-time, it was filtered, dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide, filtered and the clear solution acidified with acetic acid whereby the dyestuff was thrown down. This was collected and washed well with water, acetone and

alcohol, yield 0.6 g. This was crystallised according to the directions of Karrer (*loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 19.36. $C_{13}H_{10}O_4N_4$ requires N, 19.58 per cent).

In some experiments, wherein the reason could not be exactly traced, instead of the flavin acid, a new yellow product was isolated. This differs from the flavin derivative in being fairly easily soluble in alcohol and acetone and showing no fluorescence in alcoholic or pyridine solution. It crystallises from dilute alcohol or pyridine in golden yellow needles, m.p. 219°. (Found: C, 49.56; H, 3.92; N, 15.52 per cent). It can also be obtained as a colourless product under a particular set of conditions. It dissolves in sodium bicarbonate without effervescence and the alkaline solution shows no fluorescence. The same product could not be obtained by reducing *N*-(*o*-nitrophenyl)- β -aminopropionic acid with either alkaline stannite or ferrous sulphate and ammonia and then acidifying with acetic acid. From the analytical figures with a high oxygen content, it appears to be a product of some complex reaction. It could not be further investigated owing to the small quantity of the material at the disposal.

N-(2-Nitro-4-methylphenyl)- β -aminopropionic acid (VII, R=Me) was prepared just as in the previous case by heating an intimate mixture of 2-nitro-4-methylaniline (15 g.) and β -bromopropionic acid (15 g.) at 145-50° for 1 hour, dissolving the product in dilute ammonia, filtering and acidifying the filtrate under cooling, yield 5.5-6.5 g. It crystallised from alcohol in shining red prisms, m. p. 148-49°. (Found: N, 12.48. $C_{10}H_{12}O_4N_2$ requires N, 12.50 per cent).

From the above compound the preparation of the flavin-propionic acid was attempted following the exact conditions as in the above case. Instead of the desired product, a compound crystallising in yellow needles or flakes, m.p. 225°, formed the main bulk of the product. This appears to resemble the product (m.p. 219°), described previously, in its properties. This could not be obtained by reducing the nitro compound with alkaline stannite, stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid or ferrous sulphate and ammonia. This is being further examined.

3-Nitro-4-aminocinnamic Acid.—*p*-Nitrobenzaldehyde (20 g.), reduced by a solution of sodium bisulphite (35%, 200 c. c.) essentially according to the method of Cohen and Springer (*Manatsk.*, 1903, 24, 87), gave *p*-aminobenzaldehyde hydrochloride (28 g., Cohen and Springer get 20 g.) which was directly acetylated by boiling with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate. Even after repeated crystallisations *p*-acetaminobenzaldehyde was found to melt only at 153° (Cohen and Springer give m.p. 161°, while Gabriel and Herzberg, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2003, give m.p. 153°). 3-Nitro-4-acetamino-

cinnamic acid can be prepared from it by the following two methods:

(i) *p*-Acetaminobenzaldehyde (12 g.), dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid (100 c. c.) below 15°, was cooled to -5° and a mixture of nitric acid (*d* 1.51; 20 c. c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84; 30 c. c.) was slowly added with good stirring without appreciable rise in temperature. The mixture after keeping at this temperature for ½ hour was poured into ice, filtered and the nitrated product crystallised from water, yield of 3-nitro-4-acetaminobenzaldehyde was about 11 g.

A mixture of 3-nitro-4-acetaminobenzaldehyde (11 g.), malonic acid (12 g.), pyridine (15 c. c.) and piperidine (1 c. c.) was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour, then on the sand-bath for 15 minutes and poured into dilute hydrochloric acid (250 c. c.), whereby 3-nitro-4-acetamino-cinnamic acid crystallised out in almost quantitative yield.

(ii) A mixture of *p*-acetaminobenzaldehyde (10 g.), malonic acid (11 g.), pyridine (20 c. c.) and piperidine (1 c. c.) was heated on the steam-bath for 1½ hours and on the sand-bath for 15 minutes and then mixed with dilute hydrochloric acid (200 c. c.), whereby *p*-acetaminocinnamic acid crystallised out (yield 9.5 g., some more of the product being obtained from the mother liquors on standing).

If nitrated with very concentrated acid at the room temperature or even at 0°, there is a pronounced tendency for the compound to get decarboxylated with the production of the styrene derivative. Gabriel and Herzberg (*loc. cit.*) nitrated it at -12° to -14° with fuming nitric acid. The following condition appears to be more satisfactory. *p*-Acetaminocinnamic acid (7.5 g.) was added with stirring to nitric acid (*d* 1.42; 50 c. c.) with good stirring, care being taken to keep the temperature between 15-20°. After all the product was added the mixture was carefully raised to 25° for a few minutes, poured into ice, filtered, the product dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide, and the solution carefully acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid when 3-nitro-4-acetaminocinnamic acid separated, yield 7 g.

Hydrolysis of this product to 3-nitro-4-aminocinnamic acid was carried out according to Gabriel and Herzberg (*loc. cit.*). After crystallising from water it melted at 225° (decomp.) (*cf.* lit. m.p. 224.5°; 218°).

Alloxazine 7- or 8-(β)-acrylic Acid.—3-Nitro-4-aminocinnamic acid (1 g.) dissolved in 2*N*-NaOH, was added to alkaline stannite solution from stannous chloride (3.5 g. in 25 c. c. of water) and 2*N*-NaOH (60 c. c.) and stirred well for ½ hour. To the light brown solution obtained was added with stirring a solution of alloxan (2 g. in 20 c. c. of water) and glacial acetic acid (50 c. c.), when the yellow condensation product separated. The solution was

acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) and kept for 2 hours. Sugar charcoal (15 g.) was added to it and the solution was stirred for 1 hour whereby the yellow product was absorbed. The charcoal was filtered, thoroughly washed with water and the dyestuff eluted by means of pyridine-methanol-water mixture. The yellow solution showing a green fluorescence was concentrated to a small volume under reduced pressure when the yellow product separated, yield 1 g. It was obtained from boiling water as a yellowish orange spongy mass. (Found: N, 19.98. $C_{13}H_8O_4N_2$ requires N, 19.72 per cent.) In dilute alkaline solution it shows a green fluorescence and very easily decolourises alkaline permanganate.

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